

PARAMETERS OF UZBEKISTAN POST-INDEPENDENCE FOREIGN POLICY

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the main principle position of the Republic's foreign policy is adherence to the policy of non-alignment with any military-political bloc, preventing the deployment of foreign military bases and facilities on its territory and the non-participation of the country's servicemen in peacekeeping operations abroad, and resolving all contradictions and conflicts only with peaceful means.

“The main principles and priorities of Uzbekistan’s foreign policy are aimed at ensuring sovereignty and freedom of movement in the international arena”

Abdulaziz Kamilov

The leaders and political elites in that Central Asian countries have built a foreign policy formation shaped by their objective perceptions. The formation behind the foreign policy behavior, was not originated merely from external factors or cannot be evaluated strictly in the context of the political influence of the great powers. The specific domestic political dynamics of the Central Asian countries and the perceptions of the leaders in this context have a direct effect on the foreign policy formation. The ideology represented by political figures coincided with the worldview of the surrounding elites and political groups. Therefore long-term strategies and shortterm tactics of foreign policy making can be seen as the sum of external and internal causes. The internal political dynamics in which the Soviet tradition and the post-Soviet realities whether conflict or overlap, determine the nature of relations with the external world.

In general, a systematic analysis of the basic principles and characteristics of the modern foreign policy strategy of Uzbekistan demonstrates the deep thoughtfulness of the ongoing foreign policy, which today could serve as an exemplary model for many countries, especially in conditions when international relations are experiencing a crisis of confidence, a lack of dialogue and mutually beneficial cooperation. These distinctive features of the country's new external course, the leading role in the construction of which belongs to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, include the following basic principles.

First, a characteristic feature of modern foreign policy of Uzbekistan is pragmatism in

building relationships with all traditional partners, as well as countries of near and far abroad. In this context, our country proceeds from the tasks of internal development. Among them are maintaining high growth rates, modernizing and sustainable development of the economy, raising the standard of living of the population and ensuring full integration into the structure of world economic relations. Achieving these goals is impossible without accompanying the launched large-scale internal reforms with an appropriate regional strategy, establishing close relations with the closest neighbors, coordinating plans within the framework of international organizations such as the UN, the SCO, the CIS, the Turkic Council, the WTO, the EAEU, the EBRD and other structures.

Secondly, Uzbekistan today invariably promotes the principle of multilateralism in the country's foreign policy. Uzbekistan stands for the development of creative processes of globalization, the establishment of mutually beneficial and equal international cooperation based on dialogue, mutual trust and respect for each other's interests. Realizing this, Uzbekistan today is active in shaping not only the regional but also the global agenda, building collective mechanisms to counter various challenges and threats that directly affect the security, prosperity and sustainable development of the international community.

Thirdly, the country relies on proactivity in foreign policy and distances itself from the role of a passive observer of ongoing processes in the region and the world. This is confirmed by the fact that by now Uzbekistan has become a member of more than 100 various international organizations and a participant in more than 200 international multilateral treaties. In this context, particular attention is drawn to the activation of Uzbekistan within the framework of the SCO, the assumption of chairmanship in the CIS and entry as a permanent member of the Turkic Council.

The newly-developed foreign policy concept has a visionary perspective that only meets the new demands of the international system. Mirziyoyev's foreign policy mentality acknowledged that regional security directly affects the domestic political ground and therefore considers relations with Central Asian countries as the main priority. In the context of border issues, it has cooperated with countries that previously had problems in a more proactive foreign policy framework. In the purpose of fighting against extremist forces, Uzbekistan is trying to build strategic cooperation mechanisms with both regional and global actors. The dynamic balance considered between Russia and China has come to the fore along with the new equation emerged in the Central Asian region. In the case of Afghanistan, it is seen that the priority is to build a security net, including the US as well as Russia. With its geopolitical position, dynamic domestic political balance and sociopolitical structure, Uzbekistan is a special country not only in terms of Central Asian study and adventure of international relations. Since its independence, it has exhibited a relatively different foreign policy behavior than other countries in the region due to various domestic political perceptions, but also in terms of the general thought.

Uzbekistan has always placed great importance on its foreign affairs, and this is reflected in its Presidential decrees and constitutional statements. In the following parts of the article, we will discuss the main principles of Uzbekistan's foreign affairs as outlined in these official documents. Uzbekistan's foreign policy is guided by several principles, such as multilateral diplomacy, economic diplomacy, and regional integration.

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